

Issues with Corrupted Apps

New issue

Open

Hi,

We found two issues, causing Droidbot to get into an infinite loop (like in a Denial of Service)

[karineek/ApkVulFuzz#2](#)
[karineek/ApkVulFuzz#3](#)

These were caused by random changes to the Manifest file of the APK.

While the root cause is a malformed AndroidManifest.xml, DroidBot's failure to catch the errors results in an unhandled infinite loop. The tool should gracefully exit or skip the APK instead of hanging indefinitely and consuming system resources.

Could we implement a pre-flight check or a strict timeout for the APK installation phase? Currently, these two samples (Issue [#2](#) and [#3](#)) act as 'poisoned seeds' that stop an entire fuzzing pipeline.

@ @

Assignees

No one assigned

Labels

No labels

Type

No type

Projects

No projects

Milestone

No milestone

Relationships

None yet

Development

Code with agent mode

No branches or pull requests

Participants

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